
TRANSLATION METHODS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN “BYGONE DAYS”

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Abstract: Language, being one of the most highlights of a country, communicates the culture of the individuals who talk it, i.e. national culture. An enormous part in its comprehension is given to phraseological units. They, as collapsed writings, speak to an vital component of the "language". Phraseological units not as it were express, but moreover shape the social character of the native-speaking individuals. The ponder of phraseological units makes a difference in numerous ways to get it the culture and way of life of people groups, to ace a remote language. The world of expressiveness of cutting edge English is awesome and assorted, and each angle of his inquire about certainly merits due consideration.

Key words: Language, national culture, phraseological units, comprehension, cultural identity, native-speaking people.

Аннотация: Язык, являясь одной из самых ярких особенностей страны, передает культуру людей, которые на нем говорят, то есть национальную культуру. Огромная роль в его понимании отводится фразеологическим единицам. Они, как рухнувшие писания, говорят о жизненно важном компоненте «языка». Фразеологические единицы не как бы выражают, но более того, формируют социальный характер личности-носителя языка. Обдумывание фразеологизмов имеет большое значение для понимания культуры и образа жизни групп людей, изучения отдаленного языка.

Ключевые слова: Язык, национальная культура, фразеологизмы, понимание, культурная идентичность, носители языка, лакуны, реалии.

Moving onto the part during which the analysis on the interpretation is finished, it's important to denote how difficult could be for translators to seek out the alternatives for phraseological units of an Uzbek language in an West Germanic language. Thus, this means that two cultures behind these languages don't share the identical mentality and cultural backgrounds. This issue is taken into account within the process of the analysis. However, there might not always be similar phraseological unit within the target language, within which case the translator will use one-word correspondence, descriptive translation, and tracing. When the translating language doesn't have identical stable turnover, or when it's, but the

emotional expressiveness and elegance labeling differ greatly from the first, one-word translation is used.

In addition, even with the compensatory possibilities of the context, there's some loss of expressiveness and semantic shades in such correspondences. Descriptive translation might not affect the translation's overall creative quality, but it'll nearly always end in partial stylistic losses. Because paper within the translated text will appear as an alien formation requiring special interpretation, the technique of tracing within the translation of phraseological units connected with a word is practically utilized only very seldom. For instance, the author utilized the folks adage "kavshim ko'chada qolg'an emas" to elucidate the qualities of Uzbek character, which implies "to know one's worth" in semantic terms. Because this fixed statement has no equivalent or parallel in any of the target languages, the tracing approach, i.e. the literal translation method, was employed to translate this phraseological unit. The first reason for this can be that the foremost word within the phraseological unit "kavshim - galoshes - galoshes" is fully national, giving the changeover a wholly national character. We will discuss one in all the ways to use paper by using this phraseological unit as an example: verbatim translation of the text. Provided that there's no substitute expression within the destination language is that this sort of text transmission used. The translators handled the matter by incorporating the phrases "proverb" and "proverb" because such a translation style is usually confusing to a far off language reader and generates misunderstanding.

It is safe to mention that the nickname "xotinboz" in Abdullah Kodiriy's novel "Bygone Days" fully reflects the behavior and character of this hero. Because the author says, if the image of Homid doesn't suit the wife's heart, take the suitable one and make the wife two. If they do not agree, take a 3rd. it's a picture that acts in accordance with the concept that it's not a man's job to grieve that his wife is inappropriate. In other words, the nickname "xotinboz" is chosen in an exceedingly way that's very appropriate to his nature. The all-round clever author has even commented on the nickname himself. For example, the heroine of the novel Uzbek aim understands at one point that the sole thanks to keep her son faraway from the "Margilan sorceress" is for her to marry Atabek a second time in Tashkent to a woman she chooses herself. She first goes to speak to her husband, knowing if she will get his approval, persuading Atabek won't take long. Here, the reader gets a more robust understanding of the protagonist's personality. The reader gets a much better understanding of the heroine's personality as she exposes herself to be a really emotional, capricious woman who knows the way to skillfully maintain pity. Yusufbek-hajji is at a lost, unable to endure his wife's perseverance. Uzbek-aim "qanot-quyruq bo'ldi, like she stretched her wings and tail" in response to her husband's uncertainty. A descriptive translation of the phraseological unit was

accustomed translate this phraseological turnover into English. "Served to fan the flames of resolve" reveals to the reader that Yusufbek - hesitancy hajji's simply adds to Uzbek-confidence. It's worth noting that the descriptive translation is obtainable metaphorically, which helps to preserve the phraseological color of the expression even after it has been fully changed.

Examples of father's names are Kumushbibi binti Mirzakarim Marginoni, Otabek Yusufbek Haji ogli, Muhammadrahim Yuldosh ogli. When Uzbek names are used with surnames, they are available with the word forms "o`g`li", "qizi". Husband to Kumushbibi binti Mirzakarimboy - the son of Otabek Yusufbek Haji from Tashkent. Mullah: "Did you, Kumushbibi Mirzakarim qizi, entrust the authority to dedicate yourself to the son of Otabek Yusufbek Haji, a Muslim from Tashkent, to your uncle Muhammadrahim Yuldash ogli?" After six or seven replies, his consent was hardly obtained under the pressure of the sister in laws. In these examples, the utilization of the words "oglu" and "qizi" clearly reflects the national character of the names. The analysis of this phraseological turnover reveals that descriptive translation are often wont to successfully transmit the fabric. The approach chosen is completely determined by the translator, also because the features of the translated material and also the language into which it's being translated. Last but not the smallest amount, the phraseological unit of “Bygone Days” by Abdullay Kadyri that's visiting be analyzed is within the following situation. Encouraged by her proposal's approval, Uzbek-aim sets resolute persuade her husband of the wisdom of her plan. When he marries in Tashkent, he will relax and accept his parents' wishes - "suv quyg'andek tinarqolar." Because it's created on the idea of a comparative turnover utilizing the "dek" suffix, this term may be a comparative phraseological unit. The semantic link between phraseological unit and quiet, meek, meek is to keep mum, meek, gentle. A phraseological analogy was employed within the English translation. Now let's continue the analysis with specific examples:

1. “tomiriga umid qonlari yugurib ketdi”

“...Javobini eshitkan sovchilarning **tomiriga umid qonlari yugurib ketdi**”

(on page 40)

this is translated like this:

“*Qutidor showed undeniable sincerity and devotion to his wife in his reasoning, and the two sovchi could feel **their blood quicken as they gained new hopes for success.***”⁵

2. “dunyoga jon suvi sepib”

“*Tashqarida bir qo`sha sozandalar dutor, tanbur, g`ijjak, rubob, nay va amsoli sozlar bilan **dunyoga jon suvi sepib** shaxarning mashhur hofizlari ashula aytardilar.* (on page 47)

⁵ Mark Reese “Bygone days on page 64

In this sentence, through the phrase "sprinkling the world with the water of life", Abdulla Qadiri aims to describe how intense the wedding ceremony is becoming in Qutidar's house. This sentence was translated like this by Reese:

“ *The constant interplay of instruments resonated from the the outer yard ; the dutars, tamburs, rubab and nays were accompanied by the most renowned singers of city; **they watered the world around them** with the ever-flowing spring of their songs, caressing the ears of the guests* ”⁶

The translation of the example given above does not seem to be able to give the meaning that Qadiri wants to give. because in the original version of the work, the word "sprinkling soul water" means that the songs are very pleasant. In Reese's translation, it is far from the meaning because it is being translated directly.

3. “quvonchi ichiga sig'may”

“...birav yor-yor o'qub, tag'in bittasining **quvonchi ichiga sig'may** xaxolab dunyoni buzadir, xullas, **bag'-bug' yeti qat ko'kdan oshadir.**” (on page 48)

Through the phrase " quvonchi ichiga sig'may ", the writer is describing the people who came to the house of the box worker for the gathering of a very happy girl. Of course, this phraseology clearly demonstrates the skill of the writer. This phraseology was translated by Reese like this:

“*Other women were singing a wedding song and yelling “Yor-yor” at the top of their lungs, while yet **laught they raucously ruining the tranquility of the world. the tumult reached to the seventh heaven ...***”⁷

The translator translated these phrases directly. therefore, different meanings are reflected in the original and translated version of the work. it may be confusing to the casual reader.

4. “Ko'nglini ochmoq”

Here is the next example that caught our attention, that is, "to open one's heart". this expression means to be happy in Uzbek language. because the heart cannot be opened. this is definitely used in a figurative sense. the writer also gave the same meaning in the following sentence in the work.

“-*Mana Kumushbibi – sizlarga qizlar!. Kumushning **ko'nglini yaxshilab ochinglar, qizlar...***”(on page 50)

This was translated in English like this:

“*Ladies, we present Kumush to you! **Leighen her mood, maidens.***”⁸

This phraseology has its meaning in both versions. The translator translated in the same sense as the writer intended to use it

5. “Yeng shimarmoq”

⁶ Mark Reese “ Bygone days on page 75

⁷ Mark Reese “ Bygone days on page 75

⁸ Mark Reese “ Bygone days on page 76

This phrase means to start doing something in earnest.

“ *Agar biz shu kezda zarshunosliq uchun yeng shimarsak, ya’ni gulni guldan ajratadurg’an bo’lsaq boyag’idek esankirab, mutaraddid qolmaymiz, chunki Kumushbibi lolalar isidagi bir gul va yo yulduzlar orasidag’i to’lg’an oy edi.*”

This sentence is used by the author to describe the girls at the Kumush’s wedding. And it is clear that it is explained own meanings. If we look at translation version:

“ *if we forced to single out one flower from the arrangement as the most beautiful, our previous distraction would not apply – without hesitation, we would choose Kumush.*”⁹

Here, the translation is different from the original, not to start something, but to try to do something. Despite this, there is no violation of meaning, misunderstanding. on the contrary, it will be very clear to the reader.

6. “Ishning oldini olmoq”

“*Agar bu ishning oldini olinmasa, hukumat va mamlakat uchun natija qo’rqunchdir, taqsir*” (on page 61)

In this sentence, it is pointed out that it is necessary to stop the situation before it starts. The translation conveys the same meaning. It is correct to say that this also represents the skill of the translator

In translation of Reese:

“*If we do not prevent this plot, disaster looms for the future of our lands and governance, taqsir.*”

7. “Sho’riga sho’rva to’kildi”

This phrase actually means that an event will be negative for the speaker. here comes the soup in a figurative sense. The phrase “**boshi ko’kka yetmoq**” means to be very happy. Both of these phrases directed at Kumush in the work express how rich the writer's speech is. in the translation it is also given that I would fly to the sky. Actually fly to the sky is also used figuratively to express being very happy. so it can be seen that the translator Reese also tried to translate the phrase in the form of a phrase and it can be said that he succeeded in some way

“- *Voy sho’rginangga sho’rva to’kilsin, Kumush! – dedi Gulsin. – Men shunday erni topib teksam boshim ko’kka yetar edi!*”(on page 53)

In translation:

“*Oh poor, poor thing, but damn you, Kumush! If I had husband like that I would fly to the sky in joy!*”¹⁰

8. “Ilonning boshi”

⁹ Mark Reese “ Bygone days on page 79

¹⁰ Mark Reese “ Bygone days on page 81

This phrase means the head of a team or group. Qadiri says in this work that if the leader of that group is destroyed, the rest of the group will also be destroyed. But in the translation Reese translated directly and it may not be understandable to a reader of another culture or nation.

Example:

“ – *Otabek bilan Mirzakarim qo'lg'a olinsalar, ilonning boshi yanchilg'an hisoblanib, o'zgalarning qo'lidan ish keladigan odamlar emas taqsir.*”

(on page 62)

In translation

“If Otabek and Mirzakarim are caught **the head of the snake** will be crushed, as for the others, they are not major conspirators, your honour”¹¹

As a result, country lexicon doesn't contain a fullfledged counterpart, but it does have the same term in meaning. The Uzbek "suv quyg'andek tinar-qolar" means "be silent as a lamb, humbler than dust." the interpretation totally compensates for the original's semantic and phraseological qualities; the counterpart, just like the original, is made on the premise of comparison, but it's structurally distinct. this instance demonstrates a special method of transferring text by employing a phraseological analogue, which, just like the equivalent, has the identical meaning and phraseological color because the original but is structurally different. In conclusion, the translating practice is proven to be one amongst the foremost difficult and sophisticated ones. Therefore, the task of an expert translator requires plenty of beforehand research of author's cultural background, social rank and mentality so as to start the project of translation. There are various forms of translation mentioned within the article by the means of phraseological units of Abdulla Kadyri's two most publicly accepted works. These phraseological units are believed to own a major importance showing the Uzbek culture as its most beautiful and colorful.

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